

Barriers and methods of assessing medication adherence in geriatric populations

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World Journal of Biology Pharmacy and Health Sciences, 2023, 16(01), 080–088

Publication history: Received on 28 August 2023; revised on 06 October 2023; accepted on 09 October 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjbphs.2023.16.1.0412>

Abstract

Geriatrics patients will have different co-morbidities this can antagonistically influence drug consistence. The reason of this article is to recognize different variables liable for low prescription consistence and measures to further develop the drug consistence. Older individuals are generally impacted with ongoing sickness like Hypertension, Diabetes mellitus, Osteoarthritis and so on. All these sicknesses require long haul therapy, poor compliance in this age bunch represents medicine wastage with inflated cost of medical care and significant deteriorating of the illness with handicap or passing. The majority of human and monetary misfortune related with non-adherence can be prompted by further developing drug adherence. The point of the article is to survey the hindrances that influence prescription consistence in geriatrics with persistent ailment and giving measures to work fair and square of consistence in medication, the article additionally makes sense of about the effects of medicine non-adherence. The goal of the article is to conquered the variables that influencing prescription adherence by utilizing different measures to work on the adherence in geriatrics. In conclusion, this survey article gives an extensive examination of different variables that influence prescription adherence in geriatrics. This information is fundamental for medical services suppliers to work fair and square of medicine adherence and further administration of drug non-adherence for better therapeutic result.

Keywords: Medication adherence; Barriers of medication adherence; Co-morbidities; Geriatrics; Measures

1. Introduction

The degree to which a person's behavior complies with the prescribed medication regimen from a healthcare professional is referred to as medication adherence [1]. Patient medication compliance has always been a challenge. The elderly has a larger risk of polypharmacy than the younger population since they are more likely to have many comorbidities. As a result, they may have drug nonadherence issues [2]. Adults over the age of 50 may have many chronic diseases that necessitate multiple drugs. Improved quality of life, preservation of cognitive and physical function, and decreased risks of additional illness, comorbidity, and death are all potential advantages of taking drugs [3]. Due to the patient's worsening medical condition, more hospital and doctor visits, increasing health care costs, and diminished therapeutic benefits spending and maybe over-treating an illness [4,5]. Multifactorial elements that affect adherence have been discovered by the World Health Organization (WHO), and they have been grouped into various dimensions: patient-related factors, socioeconomic factors, therapy-related factors, condition-related factors, health care team-related factors, system-related factors etc. [6].

2. Factors affecting/barriers

Nonadherence among the elderly is linked to a variety of risk factors. These include patient factors (such as old age, male gender, low education level, physical and mental status, and health literacy [HL]), medication factors (such as the

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complexity of a medication regimen, high medication costs, and inadequate labeling instructions), patient-provider relationship factors (such as dissatisfaction with health care providers, lack of trust, and lack of patient involvement), and health care system factors (such as inability or difficulty in accessing a pharmacy, lack of follow-up, and poor treatment by untrained [7]).

2.1. Patient factors

They are assembled into the accompanying seven categories: mental state, actual wellbeing, socioeconomics, past clinical history, conduct, information or convictions of the patients and different elements Mental state factors that brought about lower adherence involved being discouraged, having lower mental capability, unfortunate memory, having less fortunate chief function, being restless and having rest aggravations. Poor dexterity, a body mass index (BMI) above 25.0 kg/m², poor physical function, impaired hearing, and lower self-rated health were categorized as physical health factors. Demographics were categorized as age, sex, education level, marital status, language spoken, culture, and ethnicity [8,9,10,11,12,13]. Having goals for one's life, having stronger convictions about the necessity and efficacy of medication, and using reminder tools were all part of MA. Believers in the efficacy of treatment and the perception that it prolongs life were qualitatively cited as facilitators [14].

2.2. Medication factors

These elements were further classified into four classifications: drug, the way it is taken, how it is handled, and other factors. Drug factors included issues with the formulation, packaging, types of medications, generic substitution, and drug storage. Drug regimen factors included multiple medications, changes to the regimen, and complex dosing regimens. Drug handling factors included the need to cut tablets, the difficulty of opening childproof containers, and logistical obstacles to medication filling. Other factors included the cost and lack of insurance coverage, adverse drug reactions, drug interactions, inadequate labeling instructions, short-term medications, and the lack of immediate consequences for missed doses [15,16,17,18,19,20]. The cost of medication would be significant, especially for older patients who have retired or come from lower income groups where food and shelter are more important than medication purchases [1].

2.3. Physician factors

2.3.1. Level of recommending

At the level of prescribing, adopt a collaborative approach with the patient. Whenever possible, involve patients in medication decision-making to give them a sense of ownership and make them partners in the treatment plan. Simplify medication administration Utilize the most simplified regimen that is possible based on the characteristics of the patient at the initial stage of drug use.

2.3.2. Speaking with the patient

Make sense of key data while recommending/administering a medication. Address the vital data about the medications (what, why, at the point when, how, and how lengthy). Illuminate the normal incidental effects and those that patient ought to fundamentally know (Patients would be more stressed and lead to non-adherence because of aftereffects that was not forewarned to them ahead of time by medical services experts) [21,22].

2.3.3. System-based factors

Lack of patient education, medication review, follow-up, medication schedule, shorter prescriptions, shorter therapies for various conditions, and a lack of community nursing services to pack medications are all factors that affect medication adherence. [23].

2.3.4. Institutional factors

A resident care taker enhanced adherence for individuals with mild cognitive impairment, according to research.³⁴ Studies that described the patient's living situation and whether they shared a home with someone else or lived alone did not agree on either [24,25,26,27]. It is also crucial to investigate the factors influencing medication adherence in order to develop an intervention approach that can increase adherence for this subgroup because they are more likely to experience poor health effects. As a result, we made an effort to research the variables that affect medication adherence with an emphasis on senior adults with chronic illnesses who live alone [28].

2.3.5. Other factors

These include not having someone to look after you, having a heavy caretaker load, not seeing an instant improvement in health, having only one common disease, having COPD, having been hospitalized within the preceding six months, and having at least one prior episode of non-adherence [23]. Older adults may face particular obstacles and difficulties managing multidrug regimens, such as cognitive impairment, functional limitations, financial constraints, utilization of multiple healthcare providers, or transportation restrictions, to name a few. Additionally, one of polypharmacy's most important possible effects would be on older adults' adherence to their prescription regimens [29].

2.4. Impacts of medication adherence

Unfortunate drug adherence was associated with the higher occurrence of illness explicit hospitalizations in the probability of all cause hospitalization was higher among patients who had unfortunate prescription adherence. Unfortunate medicine adherence additionally improved the probability of intricacies. A useful strategy for effectively managing chronic diseases and enhancing health outcomes may be to focus on good medication adherence [30]. The effects of Those sicknesses on wellbeing results and asset use can be enormous because of their inclination and possible serious intricacies. Medication is an important factor in preventing disease progression, despite the fact that behavioral factors like eating habits, smoking, or engaging in physical activity are known to influence disease prognosis [31]. Prescriptions are a fundamental piece of ongoing sickness the executives. Be that as it may, adherence to long haul treatment stays poor [32].The World Wellbeing Association (WHO) characterizes adherence to long haul treatment as "the degree to which an individual's way of behaving - taking prescription, following an eating routine, or potentially executing way of life changes - compares with concurred suggestions from a medical services supplier" [32].Unfortunate adherence is viewed as a significant medication related issue and is related with expanded trauma center visits, hospitalizations, and sub-par clinical results, which are all related with an expanded weight on the medical services framework[32,33], Explanations behind unfortunate treatment adherence incorporate sickness qualities and seriousness, therapy factors (e.g., therapy span, number of drugs, cost, recurrence of organization), and prescription secondary effects, among others [34]. what's more, patients have their own convictions and discernments about prescriptions, which can fundamentally affect their expectation to take the endorsed drugs [35]. Adherence to prescription was viewed as higher than adherence to way of life changes [36],and this perception might be related with patients seeing meds as needs be and more essential to deal with their disease, and adherence being related with a higher impression of individual command over their sickness [37].

2.5. Medication adherence measures

Various methods have been reported and used to measure compliance. Adhesion measurement methods can be divided into direct and indirect measurement methods. Direct methods include directly observed therapy, measuring the concentration of a drug or its metabolite in blood or urine, and detecting or measuring biomarkers added to drug formulations in the blood. Direct approaches are one of the most accurate methods for measuring compliance, but they are expensive. Additionally, changes in metabolism and "white coat stickiness" can give a false impression of stickiness [38].

Indirect methods include patient questionnaires, patient self-report, medication counts, prescription rates, assessment of patient clinical response, electronic medication monitors, measurement of markers physiology as well as patient diaries. Each method has its own advantages and disadvantages, and no method is considered the gold standard [39,40].The simplest way to measure treatment adherence is through patient self-report [41,42].

Table 1 Summary of five types of medication adherence measure

Measures	Target population	For primary/secondary nonadherence	Advantages	Disadvantages	Ref
Direct measure	Patients received single dose and intermittent treatment and were hospitalized.	Both Primary and Secondary non-adherence.	More specifically physical evidence can be provided.	Only produces a Yes/No result Intrusion Drug metabolism is diverse Biomarkers/drug metabolites cannot be quantified Drug-drug Interactions and Drug-food Interactions.	43,44,45,46,47,48
Measures involving secondary database analysis	Countries that allow prescription refills; have a centralized, unified computer system between prescribers and dispensers; more common for studies involving large populations	Primary non-adherence.	Capable of assessing adherence to multiple medications Can identify patients at risk of treatment failure Provide medication refill samples The full data set used is typically verified by a third party for insurance claims purposes.	Assumptions are made (medication behaviour is consistent with prescription refills and medication is taken as prescribed) Partial membership is unknown Barriers to non-compliance were not identified.	49,50
Medication involving Electronic Medication Packaging(EMP) devices	Research with small populations As a reference standard to validate other measurements.	Secondary Non-adherence.	Very accurate Determine your medication habits Determining partial compliance.	Technical support required Overestimation if the patient accidentally or intentionally activates the container Disadvantage due to bulky containers Pressure on patients.	51,52,53,54
Pill count	Routine clinical practice	Primary non-adherence	Low price Simple Can be used in various formulations Very accurate.	Not suitable for dosing or non-prescribed medication use Low rating due to filling up early Arbitrary threshold value The drug sample could not be identified	55,56

Measures involving clinician assessments and self-report	Routine clinical practice Not well suited for research.	It depends on the type of assessment and the questionnaire used.	Low cost. Easy to manage. Real-time feedback available. Flexibly adapts to different conditions. Identify compliance beliefs and barriers. Well, verified.	Unreliable. Sensitivity and specificity are relatively low. It will be influenced by the interviewer's communication skills and questions. Patient wishes may be biased.	57,58,59
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Table 2 Summary of self-report questionnaire and scales

Questionnaire and scales	Function(s)	Target population	Advantages	Disadvantages	REF
Brief Medication Questionnaire	Patients' medication behaviour Obstacles to diabetes compliance	Diabetes Depression	Self-treat depression Evaluation of multidrug regimens Reduce trainee training	Time-consuming	57,51
8-item Morisky Medication Adherence Scale (MMAS-8)	Patient's medication behaviour Barriers to compliance	All confirmed conditions	Higher validity and reliability in patients with chronic diseases compared to MAQ.		59,60
Medication Adherence Questionnaire(MAQ)	Barriers to compliance.	All confirmed conditions	Fastest administration Validated in the widest range of diseases Validated in patients with low literacy level.	Relatively short, mainly suitable for initial screening.	61,62
The Self-Efficacy for Appropriate Medication Use Scale(SEAMS)	Barriers to compliance.	All confirmed chronic conditions.	Internal consistency was high in patients with high or low literacy levels.	Time-consuming.	63
Medication Adherence Report Scale(MARS)	Barriers to medication compliance Beliefs about treatment adherence	Chronic mental illness, especially schizophrenia.	Simple scoring Strong positive correlation compared to the generality of DAI and MAQ.	Limited generalizability.	64

3. Conclusion

Adherence to medication is significant in guaranteeing that restorative advantages are conveyed to patients. Adherence to prescriptions has forever been an issue particularly among the elderly, there are a few factors that impact the drug consistence and the magnitude of the effect of non-compliance, on-consistence will prompt monetary wastage and absence of enhancements in patients' conditions, who are all with numerous comorbidities. By further developing prescription consistence with the assistance of different measures including direct measures and self-reporting methods that can work on the personal satisfaction of individuals with chronic disease.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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